

A greedy Sampling Method Based on Low-Resolution Models for Snapshot Matix Construction in Neutronics/Thermal-Hydraulics Reduced-order Modeling

Yongwang Ding¹, Han Zhang^{1*}, Lixun Liu¹, Xinru Peng¹, Chuzhen Peng¹, Jiong Guo¹, Fu Li¹

¹ Institute of Nuclear and New Energy Technology (INET), Key Laboratory of Advanced Reactor Engineering and Safety, Ministry of Education, Tsinghua University, Beijing 100084, PR China;

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803892

ABSTRACT

Reduced Order Model (ROM) is a powerful numerical method that addresses the computational challenges of nonlinear neutronics/thermal-hydraulics coupled problems, achieving high efficiency without compromising resolution. Constructing an efficient snapshot matrix via effective sampling methods is a key issue for ROMs. This paper proposes a greedy sampling method for ROM based on the low-resolution snapshot matrix X_l termed Low-resolution model based Greedy Sampling method (LGS). LGS collects the training sample set within the low-dimensional solution space by analyzing the information contained in a low-mesh-resolution (by coarse mesh size) snapshot matrix. Compared to the training samples collected directly in the parameter space, the snapshot matrix from samples collected by the proposed method captures the solution space information more comprehensively. For the ROM of simplified PWR neutronics and thermal-hydraulics coupled problem with 3 perturbation parameters, given an identical number of samples and the same model order, the computation error of ROM constructed by LGS is one order of magnitude lower than that constructed by RS.

Keywords: Random Sampling (RS); Reduce Order Model (ROM); Low-resolution model based Greedy Sampling method (LGS); Neutronics and Thermal-Hydraulics coupling problem

1. INTRODUCTION

Reduced Order Model (ROM) based on Proper Orthogonal Decomposition[1] (POD) has been widely used in various fields, such as reactor physics, thermal-hydraulics, and multi-physics coupling[2] problem. A key prerequisite for good performance of ROMs is that the solution manifold must be intrinsically low dimensional. Furthermore, it is crucial that the snapshot matrix contain adequate solution space information to comprehensively capture the solution behavior across the specified parameter domain. The quality of the ROM is primarily governed by the degree to which the snapshot matrix captures this information. Consequently, effective sampling during the offline stage becomes a critically important issue. Statistical theory offers numerous general sampling methods, such as Uniform Sampling[3] (US), and Random Sampling (RS). These methods sample directly in the parameter space and incorporate no information regarding the solution space within the specified parameter range. This limitation consequently confines these sampling approaches to only considering parameter space.

Researchers have investigated several strategies to acquire and utilized solution space information, such as Greedy Sampling[5], [6] and Adaptive Sampling[7], [8], [9] (ADS) strategies. Greedy sampling requires the provision of a posteriori error estimator for the reduced order model. However, for complex multi-physics problems, the construction of such a certified and reliable estimator is almost impossible. ADS utilize the angle between existing solution vectors to guide the adaptive enrichment of the sample set. For a problem with n perturbation parameters, a minimum of 3^n uniform samples

Han Zhang*, E-mail: han-zhang@tsinghua.edu.cn

must be collected. Consequently, for problems with a large number of perturbation parameters, the required number of samples grows drastically.

This paper investigates how to acquire and utilize the solution space information from the perspective of mesh resolution. Although a reduction in resolution affects the accuracy of the solution vectors, the key distributional information is still retained. This paper proposes utilizing a large number of low-resolution simulations to construct a low-resolution snapshot matrix. Subsequent analysis of this low-resolution snapshot information guides the sampling of the training sample set directly within the solution space, rather than in the parameter space. The proposed methodology is validated using a parameterized Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) multi-physics coupled model.

2. PARAMETERIZED PHYSICS MODEL

The validation case study presented in this paper employs a simplified r-z geometry, two-dimensional, multi-physics coupled model. This model involves solving for six variables: neutron flux, solid temperature, fluid temperature, fluid pressure, fluid velocity, k-eigenvalue. Additionally, it considers three perturbation parameters: fluid inlet temperature $T_{c,in}$, fluid inlet velocity $u_{c,in}$, and insert depth of control rod h_{CR} . For detailed information regarding the model, please refer to the reference[10].

The set of partial differential equation (PDE) of this model is composed of six equations: the neutron diffusion equation, solid energy equation, fluid energy equation, fluid momentum equation, fluid continuity equation, and power equation. The iterative solution method employs a Picard scheme where each physical field is solved in a decoupled manner. Each PDE is discretized using the Finite Volume Method (FVM) to yield a system of linear equations (1). This linear system is then solved using GMRES iteration method. The final solution of this nonlinear PDE system is obtained using Source iteration and Picard iteration for each single PDE.

3. REDUCED ORDER MODEL

The Picard iteration scheme is still adopted as the solver of the reduced order multi-physics coupled model. A separate ROM is constructed for each physical field. These single-physics ROMs are then iteratively solved by passing parameters between them. The following discussion focuses on the construction and solution of the ROM for a single physical field.

3.1. Projection based Reduced Order Model

A linear system is obtained by discretizing a single PDE using FVM. It may be computationally prohibitive to directly solve the equation (1) when the dimensionality is very large.

$$\mathbf{Ax} = \mathbf{b} \quad (1)$$

If a basis $\mathbf{U} = [\mathbf{u}_1, \dots, \mathbf{u}_n] \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times n}$ of the solution space is constructed, then the solution can be expanded as the linear combination of the basis vectors, $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{Uc} \in \mathbb{R}^N$. \mathbf{U} can be obtained by applying Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD, (2)) to the snapshot matrix $\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{N_x}]$, which aggregates solution vectors generated by a series of Full Order Model (FOM) computations. POD yields the optimal subspace \mathcal{Y}_x of the solution space by maximizing the retained energy and minimizing the reconstruction error of the snapshots within the snapshot matrix, satisfying optimality condition ((3)).

$$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{V} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathcal{Y}_x = \underset{\mathcal{Y} \in \text{span}(\mathbf{X})}{\text{argmin}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_x} \|(I - \mathbf{P}_{\mathcal{Y}_x})\mathbf{x}^i\|_2^2 \quad (3)$$

Where $\mathbf{P}_{\mathcal{Y}_x} = \mathbf{UU}^T$ is the orthogonal projection matrix that projects a vector onto the subspace \mathcal{Y}_x . $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ is singular value matrix containing descending singular values. The square of each singular value quantifies the energy of the system captured by corresponding order of the basis vector.

Replacing \mathbf{x} in eq (1) with $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{Uc}$ and projecting eq (1) on the subspace \mathcal{Y}_x spanned by \mathbf{U} yields eq (4).

$$\mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{A} \mathbf{U} \mathbf{c} = \mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{b} \quad (4)$$

Solving the reduced system (4) yields the coefficients \mathbf{c} . A fundamental premise for the efficacy of the ROM is that the solution manifold is low-dimensional. Hence, the dimension (or order) of the basis \mathbf{U} is typically very small. Consequently, the projected system matrix, $\mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{A} \mathbf{U}$ is a small-scale, dense matrix, which can be solved rapidly and efficiently using LU decomposition.

3.2. Adaptive Sampling Method

ADS techniques utilize the existing solution vectors to assess the geometric relationships among them. This assessment guides the adaptive enrichment of the sample set by placing new samples in regions where the solution space exhibits sparsity. Consequently, ADS represents a foundational strategy for acquiring and exploiting solution space information.

Figure 1. Adaptive Sampling Method Schematic

For convenience, the process of a specific of ADS sampling strategy of two perturbation parameter is illustrated in Fig. 1. The ADS is initialized by generating a preliminary training set via uniform sampling in the parameter space (step 1). Critically, while uniform within the parameter space, the sample distribution within the solution space is highly non-uniform, leading to local sparsity. To address this, uniform samples are calculated by FOM to obtain corresponding solution vectors, which provide insight into solution manifold. The core adaptive process involves analyzing the linear dependence (or geometric relationships in solution space) among these solution vectors to determine the parameter regions requiring enrichment (similar to the Bisection method). The reference [9] utilized the angle between the solution vectors as the defining metric for assessing solution space sparsity. For example, the uniform sampling process partitions the parameter space into four sub-domains, with each element defined by four corner vertices. Calculate the angle θ_1 and θ_2 between the solution vectors corresponding to two pairs of diagonal vertices. The sum of these two angles is then defined as the angle measure for that specific element ($\theta = \theta_1 + \theta_2$). A larger angle value signifies greater sparsity among the four solution vectors corresponding to these vertices within the solution space. The element exhibiting the maximum angle measure is then subjected to adaptive refinement using uniform sampling to increase the local density (step 2). Subsequently, the sample set is adaptively enriched by iteratively repeating the aforementioned procedure (step 3, step 4, ...).

3.3. Low-resolution Model based Greedy Sampling Method

The neutron flux distribution curves across a cross-section (at the axial position $z = 2 \text{ m}$) under different parameter ($p = [T_{in}, u_{in}, h_{CR}]$), comparing results from a 100×100 (high mesh resolution) and 50×50 (low mesh resolution) mesh, are shown in the Fig. 2. An examination of the curves reveals that while lowering the resolution inevitably impacts the precision of the solution vectors, the essential distributional characteristics of the solution are nonetheless preserved. Some solution vectors of training samples acquired through RS exhibit strong correlation. Performing excessive high-resolution FOM computation for such redundant samples significantly increases the computational cost during offline stage, without introducing new information of solution space to enrich the snapshot matrix. To mitigate the significant computational burden associated with redundant sampling, we propose utilizing the low-resolution solution distribution information. This approach is designed to select

samples exhibiting minimal correlation, thereby ensuring that each subsequent expensive high-resolution FOM evaluation meaningfully enriches the snapshot matrix with new basis information. Accordingly, this paper introduces a Low-resolution model based Greedy Sampling (LGS) method. This methodology achieves improved sampling by utilizing cost-efficient low-mesh-resolution computations to drive the selection process. The schematic illustration of the LGS and comparison of the sampling strategies of RS and LGS are presented in Fig. 3 (b).

Figure 2. Comparison of the Neutron Flux Distribution between 100 Mesh Resolution and 50 Mesh Resolution

The workflow of LGS is detailed in the Fig. 3 (a). The procedure is initiated by simply selecting M candidate samples $\mathbf{P}_{RS} = [\mathbf{p}_i], i = 1, 2, \dots, M$ via RS. These candidates are then rapidly evaluated using the low-resolution FOM to generate a corresponding low-resolution snapshot matrix $\mathbf{X}_{low} = [\mathbf{x}_{low,i}], i = 1, 2, \dots, M$, which contains the solution space information. Subsequently, a greedy selection algorithm is applied to the low-resolution snapshot matrix to select the N most informative parameter samples $\mathbf{P}_{LGS} = \mathbf{P}_{l \rightarrow h} = [\mathbf{p}_{idx_i}], i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ from \mathbf{P}_{RS} . These selected samples correspond to solution vectors exhibiting minimal mutual correlation. This subset constitutes the optimized parameter training set. Finally, the high-resolution solution vectors for this refined training set \mathbf{P}_{LGS} are computed using the high-resolution FOM, thereby yielding the final high-resolution snapshot matrix $\mathbf{X}_{LGS} = \mathbf{X}_{l \rightarrow h}$ for the ultimate ROM construction.

Figure 3. Workflow and Schematic of the LGS Method

4. NUMERICAL RESULT

This section utilizes the simplified PWR neutronics/thermal-hydraulics coupled model described in Section 2 for validation of LGS. Three perturbation parameters inlet temperature T_{in} , inlet velocity u_{in} , control rod insertion depth h_{CR} are included in this model.

4.1. Offline Stage

For comparative analysis, training parameter sample sets $\mathbf{P}_U, \mathbf{P}_{RS}, \mathbf{P}_{ADS}, \mathbf{P}_{LGS,l=20}, \mathbf{P}_{LGS,l=100}$ of size N are generated using four distinct sampling methods: US, RS, ADS, and LGS, at the condition that $N = 50, M = 200, h = 100$. $\mathbf{P}_{LGS,l=100}$ denotes the optimal sample set generated by LGS across different low-mesh-resolution (l), with the final high-resolution basis generation targeting the $h = 100$ resolution. Snapshot matrices $\mathbf{X}_U, \mathbf{X}_{RS}, \mathbf{X}_{ADS}, \mathbf{X}_{LGS,l=20}, \mathbf{X}_{LGS,l=100}$ corresponding to above training parameter sample sets are constructed using FOM defined by a high mesh resolution $h \times h, h = 100$.

Fig. 5. visualizes the distribution of sample set sampling by four different methods. The first three columns present the projections of the sample set onto the three orthogonal planes of the 3D parameter space. The rightmost column depicts the distribution of the first- and second-order coefficients (\mathbf{c}_1 and \mathbf{c}_2), obtained by projecting the sample set's solution vectors onto the first and second order basis (\mathbf{u}_1 and \mathbf{u}_2 of \mathbf{U}) of the solution space, which effectively represents the distribution of the sample set within the solution space.

Figure 4. Singular Value Decay Curves of Snapshot Matrices by Different Sampling Method

Samples obtained via US, while maintaining spatial uniformity in the parameter space, collapse into four distinct clusters within the solution space. These clusters correspond directly to four different control rod insertion depths. The distribution of the solution vectors within the solution space corresponding to the control rod insertion depth range of 2.667 m to 4 m is greater than that observed for the wider 0 m to 2.667 m. Consequently, the solution vectors for the 2.667m to 4m range are considered relatively sparse within the solution space. The distribution of the 50 samples obtained via RS within the solution space exhibits significant discontinuities leading to degraded accuracy. The ADS method attempted to address this issue by introducing additional samples into the regions of the solution space exhibiting the largest discontinuities relative to the initial US. However, this refinement did not significantly alleviate the effects of the existing solution space gaps. Consequently, for this specific problem, both US and ADS refinement strategy based on it proved incapable of adequately capturing the solution space information. The performance of US and RS in capturing the variations related to inlet velocity and inlet temperature was poor. This deficiency arises because the solution vectors for the samples in the center of the parameter range exhibit high mutual correlation. Both LGS and ADS method accurately captured this phenomenon, resulting in denser sampling in the bottom-left and top-right corner of the $T_{c,in} - u_{c,in}$ plane and in the right and left regions of the $h_{CR} - T_{c,in}$ plane.

A reference snapshot matrix \mathbf{X}_{Ref} was constructed by computing 1000 samples using the high-resolution FOM, defined by a 100×100 mesh resolution. The quality of this reference is confirmed by

its 1000th normalized singular value, which exhibits a minimal magnitude 1.6×10^{-14} . Consequently, this snapshot matrix is proved to provide an excellent approximation of the solution space. POD is applied to the aforementioned snapshot matrices to extract the corresponding basis vectors and singular values. The resulting spectral decay is visualized in the Fig. 4, which compares the singular value decay curves for different physical fields as obtained using different sampling methodologies.

Figure 5. Samples Distribution within Parameter Space and Solution Space

The singular value decay curve of \mathbf{X}_{Ref} is utilized as reference (Fig. 4 (a)) to evaluate the snapshot matrices generated by different sampling methods. Furthermore, since the neutron flux distribution is the most complex physical field, characterized by the slowest decay, Fig. 4 (b) primarily focuses on presenting the decay curves for the neutron flux. The rapid decay observed for both US and ADS indicates a deficiency in their snapshot matrices, as they capture minimal information about the solution space. While the performance of RS is superior to these two methods, its curve nonetheless

remains significantly offset from the reference. The decay curves for both two LGS snapshot matrices $\mathbf{X}_{LGS,l=20}$, $\mathbf{X}_{LGS,l=100}$ closely track the reference, implying that these snapshot matrices have nearly fully captured the information required for a basis of rank 50.

4.2. Computation Error of ROM

ROMs are constructed utilizing aforementioned snapshot matrices based on different sampling methods. Additionally, a test set comprising 200 samples is selected using RS for validation of the ROMs. The resulting relative computational error (average over 200 test cases) of the ROMs as a function of the model order are shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6. Computational Error of ROM based on Snapshot Matrices by Different Sampling Method

Given that the neutron flux distribution exhibits the highest complexity among all physical fields, yielding the largest error, this study primarily focuses on analyzing the error associated with the neutron flux. The error curve for US exhibits the slowest decay rate, with ADS exhibiting only a marginal improvement over US. This poor performance shows that both methods fail to accurately approximate the solution manifold for the problem under study. The RS method yields significantly lower error compared to US and ADS; however, a substantial discrepancy still exists compared to the LGS methods. Crucially, the error associated with the two LGS snapshot matrices ($\mathbf{X}_{LGS,l=20}$, $\mathbf{X}_{LGS,l=100}$) is lower than that of the RS method, confirming the efficacy of LGS in capturing the solution manifold. This successful performance provides the evidence that the low-resolution model, despite its inherent reduction in precision, retains sufficient latent distributional information to effectively drive the greedy selection process and capture the solution manifold.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The performance of Reduced Order Model is critically dependent not on the sample distribution in the parameter space, rather than on the accurate representation of the solution manifold. This objective is severely hindered by the strong non-linearity of the mapping from parameter space to solution space. This non-linearity causes conventional sampling methods, which prioritize parameter space uniformity to yield highly deficient and non-uniform distributions in the solution space. Overcoming this challenge requires obtaining solution space information to select maximally representative samples. The core challenge thus lies in acquiring this crucial information at a feasible computational cost. This

work introduces a novel strategy that efficiently addresses this constraint by utilizing low-mesh-resolution model computations to extract the essential distributional characteristics of solution space, thereby ensuring the high-quality ROM construction.

The numerical results indicate that the sampling method proposed in this paper has advantages over both conventional methods that sample directly in the parameter space and the Adaptive Sampling method, which preliminarily utilizes solution space information. When controlling for both the training sample size (N) and the retained basis order n , the computational error of the ROM constructed via LGS is nearly an order of magnitude lower than that obtain using RS. Future work will focus on extending the LGS-based ROM to practical multi-physics coupled problems.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the Nuclear Technology R&D Program No. HNKF202307(60), LingChuang Research Project of China National Nuclear Corporation, National Natural Science Foundation of China 12275150, Beijing Natural Science Foundation number 1244054, and National Key R&D Program of China number 2022YFB1903000.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Berkooz, P. Holmes, and J. L. Lumley, 'The Proper Orthogonal Decomposition in the Analysis of Turbulent Flows', *Annu. Rev. Fluid Mech.*, **vol. 25**, no. 1, pp. 539–575, Jan. 1993, doi: 10.1146/annurev.fl.25.010193.002543.
- [2] S. Riva, C. Introvini, and A. Cammi, 'Multi-physics model bias correction with data-driven reduced order techniques: Application to nuclear case studies', *Appl. Math. Model.*, **vol. 135**, pp. 243–268, Nov. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.apm.2024.06.040.
- [3] H. Liu and H. Zhang, 'A Reduced Order Model Based on ANN-POD Algorithm for Steady-State Neutronics and Thermal-Hydraulics Coupling Problem', *Sci. Technol. Nucl. Install.*, **vol. 2023**, pp. 1–15, July 2023, doi: 10.1155/2023/9385756.
- [4] P. German and J. C. Ragusa, 'Reduced-order modeling of parameterized multi-group diffusion k-eigenvalue problems', *Ann. Nucl. Energy*, **vol. 134**, pp. 144–157, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.anucene.2019.05.049.
- [5] P. Siena, M. Girfoglio, and G. Rozza, 'An introduction to POD-Greedy-Galerkin reduced basis method', Mar. 17, 2022, *arXiv*: arXiv:2203.08532. Accessed: May 29, 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2203.08532>
- [6] C. Zhang and C. Gong, 'Fast solution of neutron diffusion problem by reduced basis finite element method', *Ann. Nucl. Energy*, **vol. 111**, pp. 702–708, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.anucene.2017.09.044.
- [7] X. Liu, Z. Wang, H. Ji, and H. Gong, 'Application and comparison of several adaptive sampling algorithms in reduced order modeling', *Heliyon*, **vol. 10**, no. 15, p. e34928, Aug. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e34928.
- [8] F. Alsayyari, Z. Perkó, M. Tiberger, J. L. Kloosterman, and D. Lathouwers, 'A fully adaptive nonintrusive reduced-order modelling approach for parametrized time-dependent problems', *Comput. Methods Appl. Mech. Eng.*, **vol. 373**, p. 113483, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.cma.2020.113483.
- [9] D. Rafiq and M. A. Bazaz, 'Adaptive parametric sampling scheme for nonlinear model order reduction', *Nonlinear Dyn.*, **vol. 107**, no. 1, pp. 813–828, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s11071-021-07025-7.
- [10] X. Peng *et al.*, 'Tightly coupled multi-physics algorithm for control rod follow mode based on newton-krylov method', *Ann. Nucl. Energy*, **vol. 222**, p. 111599, Nov. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.anucene.2025.111599.